

MINERVA INFORMATICS EQUALITY AWARD CATALOGUE

Celebrating a Decade of Gender Equality
in Informatics Research and Education:
Best Practices in Europe

Minerva Informatics Equality Award Catalogue

Celebrating a Decade of Gender Equality in Informatics Research and Education:
Best Practices in Europe

Authors:

- Simona Motogna, Babeş-Bolyai University (Romania)
simona.motogna@ubbcluj.ro
- Cristina Manresa-Yee,
Sociedad Científica Informática de España / The University of the Balearic Islands (Spain)
cristina.manresa@uib.es
- Svetlana Hensman, Technical University Dublin (Ireland)
svetlana.hensman@tudublin.ie

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www.informatics-europe.org

administration@informatics-europe.org

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Introduction

The Informatics Europe Working Group on Diversity and Inclusion aims to:

1. create awareness about the problems, challenges, and values of diversity,
2. act as a collector of European initiatives on diversity and inclusion,
3. define best practices to cope with diversity through inclusion.

The working group chairs the Minerva Informatics Equality Award, which recognises outstanding European initiatives and best practices in attracting, supporting and encouraging women pursuing research and education careers in Informatics. The Award was launched in 2016 and has seen increasing interest from all over Europe. Until 2022, the Award followed a three-year cycle, each year focusing on a different career stage. Since 2023, the Award has considered initiatives at any stage of the career pipeline, including but not limited to:

- encouraging female students to enrol and persist in Informatics/Computer Science programmes;
- supporting PhD and postdoctoral researchers in transitioning to faculty positions;
- advancing the careers of female faculty through retention and promotion.

The main benefit of this initiative is to raise awareness and improve the current status, and to inspire institutions to take action.

The objective of this contribution is to offer a comprehensive, easy-to-search catalogue of good practices that have the potential to impact women's academic careers. This catalogue aims to serve as a resource and guide for academic institutions, departments, academic leadership and individuals committed to fostering gender equity in academia.

Through the openness of the contributors to the submissions and the effort of the diversity and inclusion community, the submissions nominated for the Minerva Award from 2016 to 2025 have been analysed, labelled and reviewed to create this catalogue.

Methodology

Data collection

The data are represented by the past submissions nominated from 2016 to 2025 for the Minerva Award. All submissions are highly valued by the evaluation committee and describe diverse initiatives implemented in institutions across Europe. Therefore, we took into consideration all submissions for this catalogue, not only the winners. We took advantage of the fact that, given the openness and transparency of the community, the proposers have agreed to publish their submissions even if they did not win.

Data processing

The work was split between three members of the research team in order to resolve ambiguities and avoid biases. First, consensus on processes and steps was reached. Then, the initial step was performed independently by each researcher, followed by a debate between all three members. The following workflow was adapted from existing practices of thematic analysis¹:

- familiarise with data by carefully reading and structuring the text to allow better processing;
- generate keywords: to identify strings relevant to our study;
- classify the keywords: grouping keywords into categories based on their meaning and effect; if a keyword did not match any existing category, a new one was created. As a result, this step also resulted in a set of created categories;
- review of the approach: self-assessment by the research team, with debate on keywords and categories, followed by an external audit in which an external researcher (not involved in previous steps) reviewed the results.

One of the biggest challenges was to reach a consensus between terms, for example, how to distinguish between educational activity and training. As a consequence, we defined a list of terms that is supposed to completely and unambiguously characterise the keywords. The complete list of term definitions is in Appendix A.

¹ Cruzes, D.S., Dyba, T., 2011. Recommended steps for thematic synthesis in software engineering, in: 2011 International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement, pp. 275–284. doi:10.1109/ESEM.2011.36.

Classification

Until 2022, the Award followed a three-year cycle, each year focusing on a different career stage:

- encouraging female students to enrol and persist in Informatics/Computer Science programmes;
- supporting PhD and postdoctoral researchers in transitioning to faculty positions;
- advancing the careers of female faculty through retention and promotion.

We started classifying the activities from proposals based on these three categories, which we further divided into subcategories as we identified that they were targeting different objectives. The classification process was performed in several steps: initially, one member of the team classified each entry, then the whole team debated the designated class, and for some complex cases, the opinion of the Diversity and Inclusion Working Group was investigated. The final form of the initiative classification is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Categories of initiatives

In addition, each initiative was tagged to indicate its type, purpose, and target audience. In the catalogue, each initiative contains one or more tags to provide useful details. The complete list of tags used and their description is provided in Appendix A.

Catalogue

We present the complete list of the identified initiatives grouped into categories. A searchable tabular format of the catalogue is available [here](#).

A. Encouraging female students to enrol and persist in Informatics

Comprising activities to recruit young female students (Table 1) or to retain female students in faculty (Table 2), this category consists of the initiatives describing activities outside the university, in schools, camps or within the university campus organised for young girls.

Table 1. Recruitment of students

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Ensuring diversity on interview panels	[1]	recruitment strategy
Ensuring diversity on marketing materials	[1,62]	recruitment strategy advertise
Visits to universities by female staff, and female-only student open days;	[1]	role models highschool
Attracting students from various backgrounds such as psychology and cognitive sciences	[1]	interdisciplinary programmes
Several mono- and co-educational programmes encouraging girls from 5 years (preschool) up to 18 years (senior high schoolers) to enroll in CS programmes	[2,27]	primary highschool
Website providing online information about female role models	[2]	role models
Master degree "Computing in the Humanities"	[2]	interdisciplinary programmes

Bachelor's study programme in Computer Science (CS) which is strictly single-sex during the first 3 semesters	[3]	education
BSc Computer Science (International), where each student studies a language (Chinese, German, Korean) - international attraction	[4]	interdisciplinary programmes
Free coding courses for non-tech female students	[4]	interdisciplinary programmes
Run the annual "Computing Academy" for transition year students (15 y)	[4]	highschool
Organize Technology Camp and Girl's Day event for highschool students on university campus	[5,25]	highschool
2-weeks intensive summer camp	[6,28]	highschool
2-weeks campus: training and communication activities with young female students as mentors	[8]	highschool role models
Distant tutoring	[9]	mentoring highschool
Sessions with girls (6 to 18y) and families accompanied by a volunteer	[10]	highschool primary family
Summer camp for girls (17-18y)	[11,42]	highschool
Admission Caravan	[12]	advertise
IT Camp for highschool girls	[13]	highschool

Student for a day	[13]	highschool event
Female pupil outreach workshops (11-14y)	[14,38]	highschool
Promotion of success stories to motivate female students to enrol in the STEM studies	[17,27]	advertise role models
Outreach programme providing tools, teaching materials and staff support	[25]	teaching support
Introductory courses to CS age 12-18 (newsletters)	[25]	highschool advertise
Course on Robotics for highschool (age 16-18)	[25]	teaching support highschool
Promote female professional role models	[27,36]	role models
Develop gender neutral promotional materials	[27]	advertise
Tea party with role models	[27]	role models event
Course Programming with Vaiana (Disney character) (age 7-12)	[27]	primary
Promotion of sciences to high school girls	[36]	highschool
Workshop - create artefact	[41]	highschool
International Women Degree Programme in Computer Science (IFI)	[49]	interdisciplinary programmes

Online interdisciplinary courses	[50]	interdisciplinary programmes
Workshops Women & Engineering Project	[52]	event
Mentoring and coaching programmes – ADA Initiative	[56]	mentoring, networking, advertise
Kodeløypa - coding and computational thinking training	[56]	highschool
Reskilling programmes	[57]	training
Women in Cybersecurity – Role Models for Girls	[57]	role models
Social robots workshop	[61]	highschool
School visit	[61]	highschool
Computer Science Summer Camp	[62]	highschool
Three-week summer bootcamp	[59]	highschool
Gamified programme fostering computational and critical thinking to detect early signs of gender - based violence among teenagers	[63]	education

The retention of female students in faculty refers to actions supporting them to finish their study, to diminish the dropout rate and to encourage them to continue their education (for example, for Bachelor students to enrol on Master programmes or for master students to pursue a PhD programme).

Table 2: Retention Initiatives of female students

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Female Mentorship Programme	[1, 17,37]	mentoring
Organizing female-only events such as hackathons, and support groups	[1,38]	event support group
Personalised Technical Learning Portfolio approach to provide students with a flexible working pattern	[1]	training
Mentoring and coaching programmes (e.g. "Frauennetzwerk", "CoachNet")	[2]	mentoring
Seminar course "Gender Aspects of Computer Science"	[2]	training
Mentoring in single gender programme in CS	[3]	mentoring
Each female student will be placed in lab groups with at least one other female	[4]	mentoring role models
Creation of a female student community through regular hosted meet-ups organised	[4,25]	community
Computer study room for women	[5]	community
Welcome day for new female students at ICT	[5]	event
Organize events: invited talks	[7]	event role models
Sharing stories: social media	[7]	community role models

Annual Award for women in CS	[9]	active support
Study lab - help between generations	[13]	community
Esteem student mentoring scheme - female students teamed up with female staff member and mentored by industry role model	[22]	mentoring role models
Fair procedures in teaching: in some courses grading is performed anonymously, leading to changes in the ranking of female students	[19]	education
Travel grants to attend dedicated events (Ada Lovelace festival, ISMIR)	[25,26]	financial support
Mentoring programme (worldwide outreach - virtual)	[26]	mentoring
AtariWomen - stories of women who contributed to computer games	[41]	role models
"Women Future in Computer Science" competition	[42]	event
Inclusive advertising for PhD studies	[47]	advertise
Open Days and Recruitment Ambassadors:	[47]	event
Female-focused student hackathon	[53]	event
Publish stories	[57]	role models
Podcast	[57]	role models

Contest for girls Founding Inspiring Futures	[60]	event
Mentorship manual	[60]	mentoring
Girls in ICT Day Event	[60]	event
Roundtable Career Prospects in ICT	[60]	event
Theatrical science outreach project	[63]	role models

B. Supporting transition to faculty

This category includes practices in support of guidance for academic careers (Table 3) and strategies for the recruitment of female academic staff (Table 4). PhD students and young postdoctoral researchers are encouraged through these initiatives to pursue an academic career path.

Table 3: Recruitment of female academic staff

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Devise fairer and more inclusive hiring processes (e.g.: the way job adverts are written, promoting active scouting by hiring managers, etc.)	[15]	recruitment strategy advertise
Ask female candidates to apply to academic positions (e.g. by head of school, head of research group, etc.)	[16, 18]	recruitment strategy
Appoint at least one female member in the advisory appointment committees equal or senior to the position advertised	[16]	recruitment strategy
Active recruitment of female researchers (as a first step towards assistant professorships)	[16]	recruitment strategy

Reserve staff positions especially for talented females	[16]	recruitment strategy
Create and follow specific instructions for job postings which considers gender diversity (e.g. recommendations for/from gender policies like gender-neutral advertisement texts)	[16]	recruitment strategy advertise
Promotion of success stories to encourage female candidates to apply for job positions in Informatics	[17]	advertise role models
Support long-term career by investing in funding part-time study for female staff research assistants) to undertake a part time PhD	[18]	financial support career development
Special care to the human resources policies: select carefully the members of the standard search committees and include at least one female research staff member.	[19]	recruitment strategy
Research visit that includes gender aspects	[45]	financial support
International Mentoring for a Diverse STEM-Professor Talent	[51]	mentoring
Gender-sensitive recruitment interventions - diversity support and work-life balance sections in application calls	[21]	recruitment strategy
Recruitment - gender-neutral language in job adverts	[24]	recruitment strategy advertise
Specific instructions for job postings	[33]	recruitment strategy advertise
Recruitment - gender balanced selection panels	[24, 30]	recruitment strategy
Recruitment: gender neutral language in applications, job adverts appealing to diverse groups, incl. information on career breaks	[16, 29]	recruitment strategy

The institute explicitly asks female candidates to apply to such a position and actively seeks for female candidates that may be interested	[33]	recruitment strategy
A number of professorships especially for talented females	[33]	recruitment strategy
Interdisciplinary collaboration with social robots	[61]	training

In the early stages of a career, advice and guidance are essential. This explains the large number of initiatives (106) to support guidance and refers to different activities from organising events, training, to role models and mentoring, and even financial support.

Table 4: Support to guide academic careers

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Fellowship writing workshops for PhD students and postdocs	[15]	support with applications ALL STAFF
Organise mock panels in preparation for fellowship interviews	[15]	support with applications ALL STAFF
Offer Gender Awareness Training (e.g. recommendations in the Workbook Gender Awareness Training)	[16]	training
On-going employment which is a long-term strategy to first motivate and later employ the best female students	[17]	recruitment strategy
Develop and support teaching skills: Support, with funding, female research staff to undertake the Postgraduate Certificate in Higher Education Teaching (mandatory for new academic staff)	[18]	training financial support
Development and support of confident communication: annual one-day Confident	[18]	event training

Communications and Presentation Course (including female only sessions) with an individual report outlining the key strengths and a summary of leaning points		
Mandatory inclusion workshop for all staff focused on unconscious bias to improve the quality of the working environment for female staff	[18]	training
Inclusive Leadership programme	[45]	training
Mentoring for fellowship applications for PhD students and postdocs	[15]	mentoring support with applications
Support the transition from postdoc to permanent academic posts (e.g. Proleptic Lectureship Scheme)	[15]	career development general with positive effect
Post-break awards (for maternity or career leave) meant to help the awardee's research getting back up to speed after an extended break	[15]	family-friendly policies financial support
Offer emergency childcare to attend meetings or conferences	[15]	family-friendly policies general with positive effect
Carry out Group Model Building sessions. Senior staff members, male and female, together with female junior staff had two sessions with the Effective Gender Equality in Research and Academia team	[16]	training
Active support of female staff/researchers by their managers	[16]	active support
Actively stimulate all female staff to participate in the university's mentoring programme for women, both in the role of mentors as in those of mentees	[16]	mentoring active support

Creation of the ‘Women in CS group’	[16]	community
Creation of Workgroup on gender diversity	[16]	policy
Support during and after pregnancy leave	[16]	family-friendly policies
Fellowships for women (e.g. Mohrmann fellowship)	[16]	career development female-specific positions
Network for both female undergraduate and postgraduate students, and staff members with formal/informal events each month	[16]	event community
Support and encourage nominations for awards of successful female researchers	[17]	active support
Connecting with other female researchers and initiatives (e.g. collaborations with Women in Cyber Manifesto, IEEE Women in Engineering organisation)	[17]	community
Female support group for sharing advice, ideas, suggestions, and reflections, especially when it comes to maternity leave and returning after it	[17]	community family-friendly policies
Flexible working hours when on maternity leave, and also later, when it comes to care for children	[17]	family-friendly policies
Absences are considered in the evaluation of achievements for promotions by extending the evaluation periods for the length of the leave	[17]	career development family-friendly policies
Support and encourage female PhD students to consider a post-doctoral career	[18]	active support
Mentoring for new female staff during their probation period	[18]	mentoring
Training for line manager in conducting appraisals	[18]	recruitment strategy
Offer an appraisal outcome, including a detailed career plan and immediate development needs for	[18]	career development

all staff, collated into the School Training Plan and the School's Human Resources Executive		
Create female-specific career development opportunities (e.g. attend Women in leadership in a changing world conference)	[18]	career development financial support
Develop and support teaching skills: Teaching fellowships to allow postdoc researcher to acquire teaching experience	[18]	training financial support general with positive effect
Develop and support teaching skills: offer the opportunity to PhD students to demonstrate in undergraduate practical classes	[18]	training general with positive effect
Development and support of networking and wellbeing: regular PhD and staff surveys and focus group sessions are held	[18]	community
Development and support of networking and wellbeing: networking opportunities (e.g. 'brown bag' events) including female focused events.	[18]	event community role models
Development and support of networking and wellbeing: host a broad range of social activities	[18]	event community
Mentoring system in place, with specific attention for female staff	[19]	mentoring
Prestigious tenure track fellowship programme aimed at high talent female researchers (Rosalind Franklin).	[19]	career development female-specific positions
Scholarships and Travel Grants Programme	[40]	financial support
Online library with books on diversity-related topics	[43]	general with positive effect
Career mapping in ICT	[46]	event

Mentoring programme - pairing new (young) staff with more experienced colleagues, 1-to-1 meetings every 6-8 weeks	[20,46]	mentoring
Mentoring events for female postdoc, tenure-track and professors - breakfast/lunch Also individual tailored 1-to-1 mentoring programmes	[21,43]	mentoring
Support for early career researchers -support for conferences, inclusion on PhD supervision schemes and seed-funding of research proposals	[22]	mentoring
Female staff are encouraged to mentor more junior female staff	[22]	mentoring
Role models for female staff via female school managers	[22]	mentoring
Mentoring female staff	[31]	mentoring
Mentoring: Teaching support and research support sessions	[24]	mentoring
Stimulated all female staff to participate in the university's mentoring programme for women, both in the roles of mentors as in those of mentees.	[33]	mentoring
Female research mentor	[34]	mentoring role models
Women in Computing Science Group hosting (informal) lunches, meetings and discussions	[33]	mentoring role models community
Yearly panel meetings for women with recently promoted women acting as panelists explaining	[24]	mentoring support with applications

the promotion application process and sharing general strategies		
Establishing a support network - WLHE (women leaders in higher education). Holds informal event with invited speakers	[22]	mentoring community
Sense of community - mailing list specifically for female staff	[20,56]	community
Sense of community - lunch for female staff with focused discussions around topics relevant to them	[20,48]	community
Series of monthly events including inspirational talks, interactive workshops, careers days, etc	[29]	community
Development of national network for academics at 3rd level computer science - Ingenics (The Irish Network for Gender Equality in Computer Science)	[22]	community
Team games to encourage tighter bond among female members	[31]	community
Celebrate achievements - communicated via email or news webpage (for all staff, not only female)	[24]	community
Conference series on gender equality (Fifty-fifty conference series)	[20]	education
Compulsory training for all staff, male and female, on prevention and awareness of harassment	[20]	education
Local library of books on women in (computer) science, with 'reading circles' for discussions	[20]	education

Unconscious bias training on student and staff recruitment and staff promotion	[23]	education
Mandatory training on unconscious bias for interview panel members	[29, 30]	education
Gender awareness training	[33]	education
Female-only post-doc positions (some later continue on as full time staff)	[21]	female-specific positions
Tenure-track positions for female researchers	[21]	female-specific positions
Additional tenure-track positions for female researchers provided by excellence-based career grants	[21]	female-specific positions
Coaching for award applications - sending information about upcoming awards and prizes, and providing help with preparing application	[20]	support with applications advertise
Contact potential female candidates and encourage them to apply	[21, 22]	support with applications
Workshops on grants writing, support with reviewing grants applications and interview preparation	[21]	support with applications
Actively encouraging females to apply for positions	[30]	support with applications
Recruitment - Share posts with women-only career networks	[24]	support with applications advertise
On-site childcare	[21]	family-friendly policies
Financial support for childcare to female staff while attending science events	[21]	family-friendly policies

Seminars and meetings organised between 9-5pm, with childcare options for events outside those hours	[21]	family-friendly policies
Core meetings between 10am -4pm	[23]	family-friendly policies
Away days over 2 days and residential, with option for staff to go home at end of day 1 and return for day 2	[23]	family-friendly policies
Timetabling is done with consideration of family commitments such as consideration of early morning starts or evening workloads	[22]	family-friendly policies
Flexible working hours, home office options	[21, 22, 23,24, 29]	family-friendly policies
Teaching modules prior to maternity leave are re-allocated to the same staff on their return	[22]	family-friendly policies
Females returning from maternity leave mid-semester can be allocated flexible project	[22]	family-friendly policies
Role sharing options to encourage women to engage in department leadership	[24]	family-friendly policies
Faculty who have taken parental leave can extend their tenure by up to an additional 18 months to support transition back to research.	[29]	family-friendly policies
Females returning from maternity leave are allocated the previous position	[31]	family-friendly policies
Family-friendly workplace environment, e.g. high chairs in cafes, baby changing facilities, priority parking for pregnant employees, etc	[29]	family-friendly policies
Enhanced policies: maternity leave policy (6 months full pay), shared parental leave policy, paid leave for careers policy (up to 10 additional days	[29]	family-friendly policies

paid leave a year to deal with short term extraordinary situations, e.g. caring for a sick child)		
Career grants to support career costs while attending training events and other research opportunities	[29]	family-friendly policies
Post-break award - grants after large breaks, e.g. maternity leave, to get research back to speed	[23]	family-friendly policies
Support for returners - fellowship for returners from career break	[29]	family-friendly policies
Enabling an employee to work from home in case an employee is located further from work or in case the environment at home is better supporting her productivity and wellbeing	[32]	family-friendly policies
Part-time work possibilities, e.g. after coming back from maternity leave or due to some change in private life	[32]	family-friendly policies
Funding and support for females to participate in Aurora leadership programme and university leadership initiatives	[22,24]	targeted training for females
Training opportunities for female leaders - five month programme to accelerate the development and promotion of high-potential women	[29]	targeted training for females
Anti-harassment committee: a spin-off of the gender-equality committee, whose aim is to propose actions preventing moral and sexual harassment.	[20]	policy
Explicit policies of equal chances and gender balance	[32]	policy

Making female role models clearly visible, having strong female leaders in the department in various positions (group leaders, senior lecturers and professors)	[32]	role models
Practice of inviting female reviewers and opponents to the doctoral dissertations	[32]	role models
Aim for one female member in each advisory appointment committee in equal or senior to the position advertised.	[33]	role models recruitment strategy
Funding part-time PhD scheme for staff (for all staff, not only female)	[22]	ALL STAFF
Annual performance review for all staff, allowing female staff to articulate any difficulties or aims. Conducted by school exec, majority of whom are female	[22]	ALL STAFF
Proleptic lectureship scheme for both male and females - promoting talented researchers (on non-permanent posts) to a proleptic lectureship post which automatically turns into academic post (permanent) once their fellowship is finished	[23]	ALL STAFF
All non-professorial staff (female and male) are required to submit their CV in a yearly meeting to the departmental professors, and receive feedback/recommendation on promotion	[23]	ALL STAFF
Yearly staff appraisal meetings with staff	[23]	ALL STAFF
Adopt a checklist of the proposed 48 measures in the publication More Women in Informatics Research and Education (recruiting female students, recruiting female, interviewing women,	[17]	policy

keeping women, promoting women, support measures)		
Conference “Women in IT - Sustainable Success Factors for Studies and Career”	[49]	event
Role models event	[60]	role models event
Telegram “Women at ETSII” sorority network	[63]	community
Feminine Informatics Society	[63]	community

C. Advancing the careers of female faculty

Continuously supporting females along their career encompasses diverse actions to retain them in their positions (Table 5) and activities towards raising the gender awareness of the entire academic community (Table 6).

Table 5: Retention Initiatives of female academic staff

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Return to work after maternity leave	[12]	family-friendly policies
Group “Women in Computer Science”	[25]	community
Lunch lectures	[25]	community
Mentoring programme (also for students)	[26]	mentoring
Dedicated workshop organized at a conference (WiMIR)	[26]	mentoring
Awareness events	[36]	event
Women in Data Science	[39]	community
Community-building events	[40,44]	event
Nursery rooms and childcare	[40]	family-friendly policies
Role model leaflets	[43]	role models

Exhibition	[44,48]	role models
IDUN mentoring programme	[56]	mentoring
Group and individual mentoring	[60]	mentoring

The gender awareness category groups different initiatives targeting the entire academic community with the specific purpose of discussing and promoting the principles of diversity and inclusiveness and of acknowledging the gender sensitive issues.

Table 6: Gender awareness

Initiative	Reference	Tags
Create committee to give advice on gender and diversity related issues to the faculty board and monitors the gender balance (e.g. Gender and Diversity Committee (GenDi))	[16,43]	policy
Gender & Diversity Day with renowned speakers	[16]	event role models
Consider men and women for promotion committees (When registering the reading committee for a dissertation, promoters are kindly reminded to think of men and women as opponents for the PhD defense)	[16]	role models
Advocate gender equality in STEM domains publicly, offering equal opportunities for men and women, based on merit	[17]	advertise
Promotion of success stories to create opportunities for sharing best practices	[17]	role models
Promote role models and include female academics predominantly in promotional material	[18]	role models

Unconscious Bias Training	[40,47]	training
Equality month	[42]	event
Inclusive Recruitment Practice Training for Directors, lead and the Administration team	[1]	awareness training
Unconscious Bias Training for academics and professional support staff	[1]	awareness training
Mandatory online Diversity in the Workplace training course for PhD students	[1]	awareness training
Gender perspective trainings for teachers	[10]	awareness training
Programmes of Teacher Upskilling	[14]	training
Upskill female scientists and expand their leadership capabilities.	[14]	training
Session to professionals and teachers about gender inclusion (certificate)	[10]	awareness training
Self-paced course on Promoting Gender Equality and Equity	[35]	awareness training
The equality observatory - quantitative and qualitative analysis	[36]	general with positive effect
CS game about inclusiveness	[57]	training
Training on emotional education, coexistence	[63]	training

Impact assessment

A natural question arising when designing such initiatives is: how can we ensure that it has an impact, or how can we measure the effect of our programmes? It depends on the specific action, targeted beneficiaries and cultural, organisational or regional factors.

We consider that some suggestions and concrete examples can serve as good starting points to design assessment plans for the implemented actions.

Assessment methods

We collected different methods by which the effect of the implemented practices has been evaluated:

- *Student surveys* [2,8,11,25]: appear to be the most used method, by which the participants in an activity are asked, after the end of the activity, about different aspects. This offers both a quantitative perspective (how many participants, how engaging the activities were) and a qualitative perspective (how they felt, how they appreciated the event, etc.).
- *Continuous evaluation of programmes* [2]: the monitoring of educational programmes specifically designed for diversity and inclusion can offer relevant indicators about their impact. Such an evaluation refers to students but also to courses, activities, staff participation, monitored progress and drop-out.
- *Alumni tracking* [2]: maintaining contact with alumni enables the collection of indicators about the success of educational programmes, the career paths of women after graduation, but at the same time, it can contribute to a pool of inspiring role models and speakers for further activities within the organisations.
- *Staff consultation* [4]: suggested method employs a root cause analysis of staff opinions, which can be used to identify existing problems, challenges or leaking pipes in the impact of designed activities.
- *Specialist employment* [13]: a social anthropologist or psychologist can work with the organisation in order to assess the status, to propose directions and to offer advice.
- *Kirkpatrick's 4 levels of evaluation*² [14]: as a method to assess training activities and to rate them on a 4-level scale: reaction, learning, behaviour and results.
- *Published papers* [10, 56]: if the activity refers to supporting the careers of female faculty members, then the results of their scientific work can represent an indicator of the initiative's impact.

² Kirkpatrick, D.L. (1998). The Four Levels of Evaluation. In: Brown, S.M., Seidner, C.J. (eds) Evaluating Corporate Training: Models and Issues. Evaluation in Education and Human Services, vol 46. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-4850-4_5

Impact indicators

The assessment was performed using a diverse range of indicators, specific to different actions and accountable during a set period of time. We have grouped these indicators into the targeted actions, resulting in the following list:

For actions with an impact on **academic staff**:

- % of female recruited [1,5,10,12,13,15, 16,17,18, 19,25,27, 56]
- % of female retained [1,4,12,16,17, 18, 19, 27,22,29,30,21,24,23]
- Survey outcomes on the workshop [15]
- Publications (accepted papers/1st author, etc) [17, 26, 56]
- Workshop organization [15]
- Levels of contentment [17]
- % of checks of the proposed 48 measures in More Women in Informatics Research and Education [17]
- Average score from students for pedagogical work [17]
- % of female leading positions (international projects, management positions, etc.) [17,20,22,29,31,22]
- Number of PhD held by women [17,32]
- Number of nominees or receivers for prizes, awards or prestigious tasks [17,19,22]
- Number of women as general and local Chairs at several conferences [17]
- % women who were offered a teaching fellowship [18]
- % of female researchers/staff [20, 21, 24,30, 31,32]
- % of females defending their habilitation thesis [20]
- % female staff turnover [22, 31]
- Gender pay gap [29]
- % females as lead applicants on a grant [29]
- % female applications to faculty [29]
- Number of booklets and policy documents [56]
- Number of organised conferences [56]

For actions with an impact on **students**:

- % of female students [18, 56]
- Gender ratio evolution 1st year and graduates [2]
- Female student experience [4]
- Internship opportunities [8]
- Dropout rate [13]
- Participants in mentoring programme [26, 16, 18, 56]
- Scholarships [27]

For organising **events and campaigns**:

- social media followers [7,28]
- number of participants [5,6,8,11,28,59,60,62]
- knowledge about CS at highschool level [25]

Appendix A - Definition of tags

Active support = suggests different supporting actions offered in a continuous and systematic manner. The important feature is to be continuous, for a considerable period of time (a semester, a year at least) and systematic (not an isolated action); the support encompasses proactive assistance.

Advertise = action towards publicising.

Award = award/reward/prize specific for women.

Career development = events/opportunities/fellowships specifically targeting females.

Community = group with a common goal/interest (fostering community).

Education = activity in which there exists a professor and a group of students (of any age). Its essential features are: a) part of a studying plan; b) delivers knowledge, and c) there exists an assessment method.

Event = seminar/workshop/social event.

Family / Family-friendly policies = workplace initiatives designed to support employees in balancing their work responsibilities with their family obligations and personal life.

Female-specific positions = a position created based on gender positive discrimination.

Financial support = different forms of financial aid to support research and teaching activities

Highschool = activity targeting high school education or pupils.

Interdisciplinary programmes = programmes combining Computer Science (or related subject) with a different domain.

Mentoring = sharing knowledge, experience and advice in an organised form for a certain period of time.

Policy = action, guideline, principle installed at the institutional level.

Primary = activity targeting primary education.

Recruitment strategy = systematic plan to attract and hire diverse staff in the organisation.

Role models = persons looked to as examples to be followed or inspired.

Support with applications = different forms of assistance to help with submissions.

Targeted training for females = seminars/workshops that are aimed at female participants.

Teaching support = different forms of assistance for teaching activities.

Training = activity of a shorter period, might result in a certification but not a grade, and have a narrow scope.

List of submissions:

The list of references includes the department or school, the affiliated university, the proposal title, the year of submission, and a link to the original source where available. During the review process, four submissions were excluded due to the fact that they did not fit the scope of this catalogue: one was a duplicate entry from a previous year [55]; another was a description of a community [54]; the third describes the legacy of a single individual [53], and the fourth was a private educational initiative [58].

[1] School of Mathematical and Computer Sciences, Heriot-Watt University. EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Robotics and Autonomous Systems (CDT-RAS): Female Recruitment and Retention Initiatives & Female Mentorship Programme (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[2] Information Systems and Applied Computer Sciences, University of Bamberg. The Bamberg CS30 Strategy (2018) [\[link\]](#)

[3] Hochschule Bremen. International Women's Degree Program in Computer Science (IFI) and IFI-Dual (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[4] Dublin Institute of Technology. Computer Science for All (CS4All) (2018) [\[link\]](#)

[5] Norwegian University of Science and Technology. The Girl Project Ada (2018) [\[link\]](#)

[6] Department of Information Engineering, Computer Science and Mathematics, University of L'Aquila. PinKamP - Le ragazze contano! (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[7] Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Basel. A Student Association at the University of Basel, Switzerland (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[8] University of Málaga. Campus Tech Girls UMA - Informática (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[9] Séphora Berrebi Foundation. Séphora Berrebi Scholarships for Women in Computer Sciences. (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[10] School of Engineering, University of Valencia. Girls4STEM project (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[11] Department of Engineering 'Enzo Ferrari', University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. Ragazze Digitali (2021) [\[link\]](#)

[12] Computer Science Department, Babeş-Bolyai University. No title (2018) [\[link\]](#)

- [13] IT University of Copenhagen. No title (2018) [\[link\]](#)
- [14] School of Electronics, Electrical Engineering & Computer Science, Queen’s University Belfast. Recruiting and Supporting Female Students (2018) [\[link\]](#)
- [15] Computer Science, University College London. No title (2020) [\[link\]](#)
- [16] Institute for Computing and Information Sciences, Radboud University. No title (2017) [\[link\]](#)
- [17] Institute of Informatics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Maribor. The Ladies in Informatics Initiative (2020) [\[link\]](#)
- [18] School of Electronics, Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Queen’s University Belfast. No title (2017) [\[link\]](#)
- [19] Institute of Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Engineering (ALICE), University of Groningen. No title³ (2017)
- [20] IRISA and Inria Center of University of Rennes, University of Rennes. Gender-equality and anti-harassment committees of IRISA and Inria Center of University of Rennes (2022) [\[link\]](#)
- [21] Faculty of Informatics, Vienna University of Technology. Developing the Careers of Female Faculty, Including Retention and Promotion (2022) [\[link\]](#)
- [22] Technological University Dublin. SUCCESS @ TU Dublin Computer Science Source, Career, Environment, Support for SuCEs (2019) [\[link\]](#)
- [23] Department of Computer Science, University College London. ADVANCE – increasing numbers of CS female academics (2016) [\[link\]](#)
- [24] Department of Computer Science, Brunel University London. WE-CARE (Women Empowerment - CAreers and REcognition) @Brunel Computer Science (2022) [\[link\]](#)
- [25] Institute of Computing Science, Radboud University. Radboud Women of Computing Science (2018) [\[link\]](#)
- [26] Department of Information and Computing Sciences, Utrecht University. Women in Music Women in Information Retrieval (WiMIR) initiative (2018) [\[link\]](#)
- [27] Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, University of Zagreb. #FERgirl (2018) [\[link\]](#)
- [28] Department of Computer Science and Engineering (DCSE), Faculty of Applied Sciences, University of West Bohemia. Summer week of computer science for girls (2018) [\[link\]](#)

³ Publishing permission not yet confirmed.

- [29] Genome Research Limited. Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Programme (2019) [\[link\]](#)
- [30] Department of Computer Science and Information Systems, including Lero – the Irish Software Research Centre, University of Limerick and Lero. Gender equality initiatives for the recruitment of female staff (2019) [\[link\]](#)
- [31] Institute of Informatics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Maribor. Ladies in Informatics (2019) [\[link\]](#)
- [32] No access⁴, Computer Science, Åbo Akademi University (2016)
- [33] Institute for Computing and Information Sciences, Radboud University. No title (2016) [\[link\]](#)
- [34] Department of Computing, Engineering and Technology, Faculty of Applied Science, University of Sunderland³ above³. (2016)
- [35] Faculty of Informatics, Eötvös Loránd University. Innochange: Promoting Gender Equality and Equity project (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [36] LIS (Computer Science Lab), Aix Marseille University. Gender-equality and anti-harassment committee (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [37] Department of Computer Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology. IDUN Project: From PhD to Professor (and Beyond!) (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [38] International University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina. We, GEN Z Girls in IT (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [39] Computer Science Department, Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, West University of Timisoara. Gender equality (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [40] TUM School of Computation, Information and Technology, Technical University of Munich. Women in CS@TUM: Female Students Support, Encouragement and Retention Initiatives (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [41] Department of Computer Science, University of Copenhagen. FemTech.dk (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [42] Computer Science Department, University of Technology Compiegne. Promoting computer science among young women (2023) [\[link\]](#)
- [43] Department of Information and Computing Sciences, Utrecht University. Women in Information and Computing Sciences (WICS) network (2023) [\[link\]](#)

⁴ Permission to publish not granted.

- [44] Steering Committee of “Alice & Eve: a celebration of women in computing” initiative. Alice & Eve: a celebration of women in computing (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [45] Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology and Gothenburg University. GENIE: GEndeR INitiative for Excellence, Informatics (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [46] University of Coimbra. INSPIRA (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [47] Centre for Doctoral Training in Natural Language Processing, University of Edinburgh. No title (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [48] Hochschule Bremen – City University of Applied Sciences. The International Women’s Degree Program in Computer Science (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [49] Department for Interdisciplinary Didactics & Department for Informatics, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. RockStartIT project (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [50] Delft University of Technology. F+Cube, the Future Female+ Faculty mentorship program (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [51] Faculty of Computer Science, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia. Workshops on Women & Engineering: Transforming invisible societal challenges into visible and sustainable achievements (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [52] Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Vrije University Amsterdam. Hack4Her: Hackathon for Female Students in the Netherlands (2024) [\[link\]](#)
- [56] Department of Computer Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology. Sustaining Gender Diversity Over Three Decades (2025) [\[link\]](#)
- [57] Department of Computer Science, Tallinn University of Technology. TalTech - Diversifying IT (2025) [\[link\]](#)
- [59] Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology and University of Gothenburg. Girls Code Club (2025) [\[link\]](#)
- [60] Department of Informatics Engineering, University of Coimbra. INSPIRA (2025) [\[link\]](#)
- [61] Educational Technology Laboratory, Intelligent System and Analytics Research group, Department of Computer Science, Norwegian University of Science and Technology. No title (2025) [\[link\]](#)

[62] Department of Computer Science and Mathematics, University of Passau. Promoting High School Girls in a Computer Science Summer Camp (2025) [\[link\]](#)

[63] Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Informática, University of Seville. NO Title (2025) [\[link\]](#)

Excluded from the systematic review:

[53] Department of Computer Science, University College London. Rae's legacy (2023)

[54] Women in Cryptography Community. Women in Cryptography (WinC) (2024)

[55] Department of Information and Computing Sciences, Utrecht University. No title (2024)

[58] HK Unicorn Squad, Estonia (2025)

For enquiries and feedback about this publication,
please contact administration@informatics-europe.org.

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